

Synthesis of a polystyrene anchored Schiff base and its complexes with some 3d-transition metals

Santwana Gaur* and Beena Sharma

Department of Chemistry J. N. V. University, Jodhpur-342 006, India

Manuscript received 20 August 2002, revised 25 March 2003, accepted 16 April 2003

Novel polystyrene supported coordination compounds have been synthesized by the reaction of metal salt/metal complex with the polystyrene supported Schiff base (PS-LH) (obtained by the reaction of chloromethylated polystyrene, coumarin-3-carboxylic acid and ethanol amine). The complexes were characterized by elemental analyses, IR, electronic, ESR spectral and magnetic susceptibility measurements.

The present paper describes the synthesis and characterization of coordination compounds of Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, U^{VI} and Cu^{II} with the polystyrene supported Schiff base (PS-LH) derived from chlorinated polystyrene coumarin-3-carboxylic acid and ethanol amine.

Results and discussion

PS-LH and its metal complexes (Table 1) are insoluble in water and alcohols. The metal binding capacity of PS-LH is 44.3–74.0 mmol of metal per g of resin. The coordinated DMF molecule is lost completely upon heating the compounds in air.

The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ (azomethine) and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ (alcoholic) stretches occur at 1630 and 1220 cm^{-1} , respectively and

shift by 5–30 cm^{-1} in the metal complexes, indicating tridentate chelation by PS-LH with oxygen and nitrogen donor atoms¹. DMF shows a band at 1680 cm^{-1} (C=O), which shifts to lower energy by 10–30 cm^{-1} in the metal complexes, indicating oxygen coordination of DMF². PS-LUO₂.DMF shows the $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O})$ at 905 cm^{-1} and this band occurs in the usual range (870–950 cm^{-1}) observed for the majority of *trans*-UO₂ compounds³. The force constant ($f_{\text{u-o}}$) and the U–O bond length in the present dioxouranium(VI) compound are 6.90 $\text{mdyn}/\text{\AA}$ and 1.84 \AA respectively. These values are in the expected range (6.58–7.03 $\text{mdyn}/\text{\AA}$ and 1.60–1.92 \AA) as reported for the majority of UO₂^{II} compounds⁴.

The magnetic moments of polystyrene-anchored Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Fe^{II}, U^{IV} and Mn^{II} (Table 1) indicate the magnetically dilute nature of the compounds⁵. The presence of polymer backbone prevents the M–M interaction in polystyrene-anchored compounds and this leads to a magnetically dilute environment around the metal ions.

Electronic spectra of the compounds could not be recorded as the compounds did not form a good mull and hence the reflectance spectra were recorded. The compounds being insoluble in common solvents, the electronic spectra in solution also could not be recorded. The copper(II) compound exhibits a band at 17600 cm^{-1} characteristic of square-planar CuNO₃ coordination sphere⁶. The absence of a band at 8000–10000 cm^{-1} rules out the presence of tetrahedral structure⁷. The polystyrene-anchored nickel(II) compound exhibits three bands at 8600, 15200, 21500 cm^{-1} due to spin allowed transitions, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ (ν_1), ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2), and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3), respectively, in an octahedral symmetry. The ν_2/ν_1 value for the nickel(II) compound is 1.77, which lies in the usual range (1.60–1.82) reported for the majority of octahedral nickel compounds⁸. The lower value of B' in comparison to the free-ion value of

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of compounds

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % :		Metal binding capacity $\times 10^{-2}$ mmol/g of resin	μ_{eff} B.M.
		Found/(Calcd.) M	DMF		
PS-LNi.3DMF	Green	3.8 (3.8)	13.9 (14.2)	64.7	3.42
PS-LCo.3DMF	Brown	3.1 (3.1)	11.5 (11.5)	52.6	4.77
PS-LMn.3DMF	Brown	3.3 (3.3)	13.1 (13.2)	60.0	5.88
PS-LFeCl.3DMF ^a	Brown	4.1 (4.1)	10.7 (10.8)	73.4	5.87
PS-LUO ₂ .DMF	Orange	10.6 (10.6)	3.2 (3.3)	44.5	–
PS-LCu.DMF	Brown	4.7 (4.7)	5.3 (5.3)	74.0	1.86

^aCl % Found/Calcd. : 2.6 (2.63).

971 cm^{-1} and δ value suggest the covalent nature of the cobalt(II) compound. The compound show bands at 8300, 12500 and 17860 cm^{-1} due to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(\nu_1)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(\nu_2)$, and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)(\nu_3)$ transitions. The polystyrene-bound iron(III) compound exhibits three bands at 12730, 19570, 24800 cm^{-1} due to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$, and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$ transitions, respectively, in an octahedral symmetry⁸. It is of interest to note that although both Mn^{II} and Fe^{III} have ${}^6A_{1g}$ ground value, all the bands occur in Fe^{III} compound at lower energy than those of Mn^{II} compound. This is due to lower value of Racah parameters (B and C) in the iron(III) compound in comparison to those of manganese(II) compound⁸. Three bands at 18340, 22990, 25220 cm^{-1} respectively for ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$, and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}(G)$ transitions are expected in an octahedral environment for Mn^{II} compounds.

The presence of diamagnetic large polymer resulted in good ESR spectrum for Cu^{II} compounds with $g_{\parallel} = 2.31$ and $g_{\perp} = 2.06$ indicating the tetragonal symmetry about the Cu^{II} ion. The parameters are as : $A_{\parallel} = 164 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $A_{\perp} = 83 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $G = 3.18$, $(\alpha')^2 = 0.81$, $\alpha^2 = 0.54$, $K = 0.31$ and $P_d = 1.91 \times 10^{-2} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which confirms the unpaired electrons in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital. In the present case values of $(\alpha')^2$, α^2 , K , P_d and g_{\parallel} indicate the covalent nature of the M-L bond⁹ and G being 3.18 shows the strong field ligand. No band $\sim 1500 \text{ G}$ due to $\Delta M_s = 2$ transition precludes the presence of M-M interaction. From the chlorine content calculation it is believed that metal atoms are placed on phenyl rings (of polystyrene) resulting in magnetically dilute environment with no M-M interaction.

Experimental

Chloromethylated polystyrene (PS-Cl) (containing 1.7 mmol Cl per g of resin and 2% cross-linked with divinyl benzene; Fluka) and metal acetates were used. The metal contents and the coordinated DMF were analysed⁴. Magnetic susceptibilities were determined by the Gouy method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NSC})_4]$ as the calibrant. The diamagnetic correction was calculated using the Pascal's constant and following a procedure specially designed for polystyrene anchored compounds⁴. The susceptibilities were corrected for temperature independent paramagnetism term using following values : Cu^{II} (60×10^{-6} cgs units), Ni^{II} and Co^{II} (200×10^{-6} cgs units), Fe^{III} and Mn^{II} -zero. Reflectance spectra were recorded on a Beckman DU spectrophotometer

and IR on Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer using polystyrene as a calibrant.

Polystyrene-coumarin-3-carboxylate (PS-CC) : Chloromethylated polystyrene (PS-Cl) (1.0 g) was swelled in DMF (20 ml) for 45 min. To this, a solution of coumarin-3-carboxylic acid (0.89 g, 4.68 mmol) in DMF (20 ml) was added followed by ethyl acetate (100 ml) and triethylamine (1.5 g, 15 mmol). The mixture was refluxed for 8 h while stirring magnetically. It was then cooled to room temperature and the yellow coloured resin was washed with DMF and ethyl acetate and dried *in vacuo* at room temperature.

Polystyrene-anchored Schiff base (PS-LH) : Polystyrene coumarin-3-carboxylate (1.0 g) was swelled in DMF (50 ml) for 45 min. To this suspension, a DMF solution (50 ml) of ethanol amine and ethyl acetate (100 ml) was added with stirring and was refluxed for 8 h, then cooled to room temperature and the dark yellow coloured polystyrene-anchored ligand was washed and dried.

Syntheses of PS-LM.x.DMF [where $M = \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}, \text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Mn}^{\text{II}}, \text{Fe}^{\text{III}}$, and UO_2^{II} and $x = 1, 2$ or 3] : To the PS-LH (0.5 g) suspended in DMF (20 ml) for 45 min, a DMF solution (30-50 ml) of appropriate metal acetate (1.17 mmol) was added, refluxed, cooled and dried.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (S.G.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

1. A. Syamal and D. Kumar, *J. Less-common Met.*, 1980, **71**, 113.
2. A. Syamal and M. M. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1992, **31**, 110; 1993, **32**, 42.
3. E. C. Alyea, A. Malik and A. K. Kazi, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1981, **6**, 223.
4. A. Syamal and M. M. Singh, *React. Funct. Polym.*, 1993, **21**, 45, 149.
5. F. A. Cotton, G. Wilkinson, C. A. Murillo and M. Bochmann, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", 6th. ed., Wiley, New York, 1999.
6. A. Syamal and K. S. Kale, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1979, **4**, 298.
7. D. W. Warad, C. D. Satish, V. H. Kulkarni and C. S. Bajgur, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2000, **39**, 415.
8. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 2nd. ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1984.
9. R. L. Dutta and A. Syamal, "Elements of Magnetochemistry", 2nd. ed., Affiliated East-West Press, New Delhi, 1993.